

Coordination Polymers of some First Row Transition Metals

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This paper describes the synthesis and characterisation of some new coordination polymers derived from poly Schiff base (PSB) and first row transition metal ions. It study showed that the metal ions are coordinated through oxygen of hydroxy group and nitrogen of adjacent azomethine group. The decomposition temperatures of the polymeric chelates were found to be in the order : Ni > Co > Cu > Mn and the thermal activation energy in the order, Ni > Cu > Co > Mn. Probable structures of these compounds have been proposed on the basis of elemental analyses, electronic spectra, ir spectra, and TG analysis.

THE first row transition metals are characterized by their ability to form a wide range of coordination complexes in which the octahedral, tetrahedral and square-planar stereochemistry predominate. This inspired us to prepare a polymeric ligand which would be able to form complexes with a variety of transition metals. This communication describes the preparation and characterisation of chelates prepared from PSB derived from 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-dipropyl biphenyl with *o*-dianisidine. The stereochemistry of the polychelates has been studied by electronic spectra, ir, magnetic moment, TG analysis and elemental analysis.

Experimental

All the metal acetates used in the present work were of A.R. Grade. All the solvents were used after double-distillation.

C and H analyses were made on a Coleman C-H-N analyser. The metal content was determined by EDTA titration technique after decomposition of the polychelates. The magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouv method at room temperature. The ir spectra in KBr phase in the range 3 600-450 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Carl Zeiss Jena UR-10 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. The TG analysis was carried out on Linseis thermogravimetric analyser.

Preparation of PSB: The ligand (PSB) was prepared from hydroxy ketone 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-dipropyl biphenyl (DDPBP) and *o*-dianisidine as described below.

DDPBP and *o*-dianisidine were dissolved separately in ethanol in stoichiometric proportion and were mixed and refluxed for 8 h. It was cooled and a dark yellow coloured PSB was separated out. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried. It was insoluble in common organic solvents but

found soluble in DMF, DMSO and H_2SO_4 . The reaction path way is shown below,

Preparation of chelates: Equimolar quantities of metal acetates and PSB were dissolved separately in DMF and mixed. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The hot solution was poured into crushed ice. The precipitates were allowed to settle down, filtered, washed with hot water and dried. They were purified by soxhlet extraction in methanol to remove impurities and dried.

Results and Discussion

The polychelates are insoluble in common organic solvents and are dark in colour. Elemental data are given in Table 1. From the data, it is revealed that all the polychelates have general formula $[\text{ML}]_n$.

Infrared spectra: On comparison of infrared spectra of ligand and its polychelates, it is inferred that they are virtually identical with each other. However, they show important differences. Strong band of C=N in the ligand at 1 620 cm^{-1} shows

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, COLOUR AND DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE

Sl. no.	Compd	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	M
1.	PSB	Dark yellow	320	75.20 (75.88)	6.12 (5.92)	—
2.	[Cu PSB].2H ₂ O	Brick red	250	64.10 (63.62)	5.90 (5.30)	10.12 (10.52)
3.	[Ni PSB.2H ₂ O]	Brown	290	64.70 (64.13)	5.10 (5.34)	9.60 (9.80)
4.	[Co PSB].2H ₂ O	Brown	270	63.82 (64.11)	5.68 (5.34)	9.40 (9.83)
5.	[Mn PSB.2H ₂ O]	Brick red	240	64.05 (64.54)	4.98 (5.37)	9.55 (9.23)

TABLE 2—TG, ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF PSB AND POLYCHELATES

Sl. no.	% Weight loss at temp. (°C)						Energy (cm ⁻¹)		μ_{eff} B.M.	E _a kcal mol ⁻¹	B _{1s}	β_{1s}	LFSE kcal mol ⁻¹
	100	200	300	400	500	600	Found	(Calcd)					
1.	0.0	0.0	0.5	10.0	32.0	44.5	—	—	—	16.35	—	—	—
2.	1.5	7.5	23.0	58.0	71.0	79.5	15.750 18.350 24.390	—	1.89	13.50	—	—	—
3.	0.5	6.0	23.5	61.5	80.0	83.5	9.615 (9.615) 16.665 (15.253) 23.095 (24.507)	—	2.64	15.47	727.66	0.673	33.0
4.	4.0	11.5	40.0	81.0	85.5	88.0	(4.181) 9.045 (9.567) 16.805 (16.281)	—	3.58	9.85	887.07	0.792	14.34
5.	0.0	4.5	24.5	65.0	82.0	88.0	14.400 16.600 20.000	—	5.25	5.22	—	—	—

either a positive shift¹ or a negative shift² in polychelates. In Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ polychelates, it is shifted to higher frequency, *i.e.* at 1 630 and 1 625 cm⁻¹, respectively. While in Ni²⁺ and Mn²⁺ polychelates, it is shifted to lower frequency, *i.e.* at 1 595 and 1 590 cm⁻¹, respectively. The observable shift obtained in C=N stretch after complexing confirms the formation of a coordinate bond from imine nitrogen to the metal ion. The medium band observed at 1 270 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is ascribed the phenolic C—O stretching vibration and on complexation does not show marked shift indicating that this frequency is not so sensitive to the chelation³. The spectrum of the ligand shows a broad and weak band in the region 2 710-2 830 cm⁻¹ and is assigned to the intra-molecular hydrogen bonded OH group. On complexation, this band disappears indicating metal-oxygen bond formation in the polychelates³. Weak band in PSB and polychelates observed around 2 890 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C—H stretching vibration. All the complexes contain weak to medium intensity broad band in the region 3 300-3 600 cm⁻¹, and a weak band around 790 cm⁻¹. These bands are assigned to ν_{OH} of water.

Nature of water molecules (coordinated or lattice) is confirmed by TG analysis. In all the polychelates, the observed band in the neighbourhood of 500 cm⁻¹ may be identified as M—N stretching frequency⁴.

Thermal study: Thermal decomposition studies (Table 2) were made by heating the compound (~50 mg) at various temperatures in a furnace starting from 20°. The temperature was allowed to increase at a rate of 10° min⁻¹. Thermal stability studies of the polymeric metal chelates up to the decomposition point indicate that they are thermally stable. The weight losses of Ni²⁺ and Mn²⁺ polychelates at 200-225° are 6.00 and 6.5%, respectively. These weight losses correspond to two coordinated water molecules per repeating unit of polychelate. The Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ polychelates show weight losses at 125-150° equal to 6.0 and 7.0%, respectively. These weight losses correspond to two lattice water molecules. The decomposition temperature of the PSB and its polychelates decreases in the order,

Goodwin and Bailar⁵ observed the given thermal stability order for the polychelates as Ni > Cu > Co which is in agreement with the observation reported by Marvel and Torkoy⁶. We have observed the same order at 200° which does not remain unchanged up to 600° as Mn > Ni > Cu > Co. The thermal activation energy was calculated by employing the Broido method and values are summarised in Table 2.

Electronic and magnetic study: The diffuse electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} polychelate shows three bands at 15 750, 18 350 and 24 390 cm⁻¹, the first two bands may be due to the d-d transition which suggests the square-planar stereochemistry⁷. Intense band at 24 390 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to charge transfer or intra-ligand transition⁸. The room temperature magnetic moment of Cu^{II} polychelate is 1.89 B.M. which also supports the square-planar geometry⁹. Ni^{II} polychelate exhibits three bands at 9 615, 16 665 and 21 095 cm⁻¹. The position of these bands are consistent with those of an octahedral, essentially distorted structure¹⁰. These bands can be assigned to the transitions ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F), → ³T_{1g}(F) and → ³T_{1g}(P), respectively. The magnetic moment value is 2.64 B.M. Subnormal magnetic moment value may be indicative of polymeric structure of the complex¹¹. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of Co^{II} polychelate shows two bands at 9 045 and 16 805 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned to ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁(F) and → ⁴T₁(P) transition, indicative of tetrahedral geometry of the chelate¹². The magnetic moment is 3.58 B.M. This low value of magnetic moment is indicative of mixture of low-spin square-planar and high-spin tetrahedral stereochemistry¹³. The Mn^{II} polychelate exhibits the transition sextet → quartet. The ground term is ⁶A₁(S) and exhibits three weak absorption maxima, one at 14 400 cm⁻¹ which may arise due to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(⁴G), another at 16 600 cm⁻¹, assigned to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(⁴G) and the third at 20 000 cm⁻¹, assigned to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_g ⁴A_{1g}(⁴G)

for Mn^{II} ion in octahedral environment¹⁴. The magnetic moment is 5.25 B.M., lower than that generally observed for spin-free d⁵ system. Lower magnetic moment may be due to aerial oxidation of Mn^{II} → Mn^{III} during the preparation of the complex¹⁴.

From the elemental, magnetic, reflectance and infrared studies, it is concluded that the metal ion is coordinated to positions on two (or more) neighbouring ligand chains indicating the polymeric structure.

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References

1. D. H. BUSH and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1137.
2. K. LAL, J. SINGH and S. P. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, 40, 359.
3. N. S. BIRADAR and V. H. KULKARNI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 3781.
4. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
5. H. A. GOODWIN and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 2467.
6. C. S. MARVEL and N. TORKOY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 832.
7. L. D. DAVE, H. K. KOTHARI and P. SUDHAMSHUMOULI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 771.
8. J. MALAVIYA, P. R. SHUKLA and L. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 1706.
9. A. KAPAH, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 444.
10. D. K. RASTOGI and K. C. SHARMA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 36, 2219.
11. V. K. ARORA, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 656.
12. M. N. PATEL and S. H. PATIL, *J. Macromol. Sci., Chem.*, 1982, 17, 675.
13. M. CALVIN and C. H. BARKLEW, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2267.
14. K. DAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 641.